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Titel

Impact of Flow Interruption on Transport and Retention
of Iron Oxide Colloids in Quartz Sand

Abstract

The mobility of iron oxide colloids in soils is of relevance due to their role in soil-forming processes as well as their capacity to act as "shuttles" for the transport of adsorbed contaminants. The aim of this study was to determine the effects of flow interruption on transport and retention of colloidal iron oxides with consideration of chemical surface properties of colloids and solid matrix.

For that, breakthrough behavior of negatively charged, organic matter-coated goethite (OMCG) colloids was investigated under continuous and stagnant flow conditions in saturated quartz sand columns. Classic DLVO and extended DLVO (XDLVO) interaction energies including Lewis acid/base parameters were estimated from sessile drop contact angle and zeta potential measurements of quartz and colloids.

Results show that OMCG colloids are highly mobile under continuous flow conditions, which can be predicted by unfavorable attachment conditions estimated with both DLVO and XDLVO approaches. These findings are in agreement with previous research. In contrast, phases of flow interruption lead to the retention of a significant amount of OMCG colloids. The colloids cannot be remobilized from the quartz sand by re-establishment of flow. Colloid retention increases with the duration of flow interruption; OMCG colloids are almost completely retained after 5 days. Sedimentation experiments show fast gravitational settlement of OMCG colloids onto the sand matrix at stagnant flow conditions.

We conclude that OMCG colloids are highly mobile under continuous flow conditions, which is consistent with both DLVO and XDLVO approaches. However, phases of flow interruption lead to significant colloid retention. It is likely that sedimentation facilitates colloid capture at favorable retention sites on the quartz sand surfaces originating from chemical heterogeneities and roughness. Under continuous flow conditions, this retention mechanism is hindered by hydrodynamic drag forces.